

ELECTRONIC PLATFORM "CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION" AND PROCESS OF TRAINING OF TEACHING STAFF

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Abstract: In this article, it was created as a system for organizing online professional development of leading personnel and pedagogues working in the field of public education of Uzbekistan. Conveniences and opportunities of the special electronic platform "Continuous professional education" are highlighted. Ways to improve the quality of education in professional development through this platform are described.

Key words: "Continuous professional education" special electronic platform, online training, onlinedu.uz, distance learning.

Introduction. It is known that the quality of education, the development of the young generation into a mature and all-round potential is closely related to the knowledge and skills of pedagogues. It is no exaggeration to say that the "Covid-19 pandemic and severe weather cooling" spread in many countries over the past 5 years has increased our need for e-courses 3-4 times. At the same time, they are relying on online educational platforms for the training of public education workers. The training system has been emerging in recent years on the basis of new modern technologies of information and communication technologies, online education and distance learning. The modern method of distance learning through online course platforms is said

to be effective enough now.

Methodology. According to the decision of the President of Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2021 "On measures to support scientific and research activities in the field of public education and introduce a system of continuous professional development" on the radical renewal of the field of professional development a new procedure was introduced. That is, according to the current regulations, public education workers, including teachers, were involved in a one-month training course every 5 years. Now they can continuously improve their skills throughout the year instead of once every 5 years. Therefore, "lifelong professional development education" is being introduced, which provides for the regular professional development of public education workers. According to the previous regulation, only 20% of the teachers were involved in professional development every year, but according to the new regulation, 100% of the teachers are trained throughout the year. Employees of public education can improve their qualifications not only at the training institutions under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations but at their own discretion, at any higher education institution or non-governmental educational organizations located in the regions. These trainings are completely free and are carried out through an electronic platform. That is, the teacher has the opportunity to study at any time and in any area. Starting from March 1, 2021, qualification improvement for science methodologists of district public education departments through the "Continuous Vocational Education" electronic platform of the scientific research institute named after Abdulla Avloni has been launched.

Special electronic platform "Continuing professional education" (hereinafter - electronic platform) - creation, storage and presentation of the

contents of educational modules to learners, as well as registration of learners and a special electronic software system that allows learning modules online. This platform was created as a system for organizing online professional development of managers and pedagogues working in the public education system. The platform provides an opportunity to effectively use the opportunities offered in the age of high technologies and to save time, to improve qualifications at a convenient time and at an acceptable pace for the learner. The platform has a convenient interface, educational-methodical complex and video lessons of more than 50 courses prepared by qualified specialists in all directions are posted.

The listener - is a public education employee admitted to a retraining or advanced training course at a specialized educational organization;

Specialists - persons working as methodologists, defectologists, speech therapists, psychologists, librarians and specialists in public education organizations;

Pedagogical staff - teachers and educators who carry out educational activities in public education organizations;

Manager employees - are persons who perform management functions and tasks in public education organizations and their structural units, as well as their deputies, as well as specialists of regional management bodies in the public education system.

To use the special electronic platform, pedagogues and managers are directed to the onlinedu.uz website. It is possible to access the platform through different gadgets at the same time: Mobile phone, Notebook, Netbook, Macbook, Smart TV, Tablet.

The interface of the electronic platform is designed to be simple and

convenient for the user, and instructions are placed in the main window. There are answers to frequently asked questions. (Fig. 1)

Figure-1

The user can also choose the language he likes (Uzbek/Russian). In addition, the main window of the special electronic platform has the following sections. (Figure 2)

- Registration system,
- Opinions of international experts,
- Certificate validation window,
- Popular courses,
- Webinars conducted by experts,
- Information about the experts of the platform is provided.

Figure-2

A personal cabinet has been created for each listener on the platform. Trainees have the option to independently choose online or offline training.

Diagnostic tests for determining professional competencies have been developed for the purpose of individual approach to the trainees who attended training. The diagnostic test helps to determine the professional component of the trainee before the qualification. In order to ensure that the test results are understandable and visual, the trajectory of individual professional development is depicted graphically (Fig. 3).

Figure-3

Based on the test results, the needs of the listener are formed and courses are offered based on the needs [2].

Currently, the possibility of independent training by choosing two or more directions through one account has been created. Now, when each pedagogic employee is engaged in pedagogical activity in several subjects, there is no need to register on the platform with a separate phone number for each subject. For this purpose, entering the listener's profile, additional information about the position and department of the subject is entered. Also, within the directions entered by the listener, the platform offers an offer on which subject to start studying. Now, teaching staff do not have to apply to admins for this, asking them to change their subject. Training courses in subjects are carried out consecutively.

There are video lessons, presentations and necessary literature by subject matter experts. In order to improve the quality of the course and the attention of the listeners, tests are given on the topic during the viewing of the video lessons. These quizzes help determine the level of mastery after each presentation. After the

student has collected the minimum amount of credit, a certificate will be presented in electronic form. Every teaching staff can download this certificate at any time.

In addition, in order to ensure the quality of professional development, the "Continuous Professional Education" platform has the following opportunities:

- An opportunity to view a personal portfolio for each listener; Ability to collect credit through alternative forms of professional development;
- Possibility of a webinar system for an unlimited number of listeners at an unlimited time; Possibility to organize various online surveys during the webinar;
- Possibility of mutual communication and file exchange between listeners and tutors; Ability to view statistical information about students on the platform;
- The ability of methodists and school leaders in the field of science to monitor students in their educational institution through the platform.
- A chat for answering questions about the LMS platform has been launched, and it is possible to get answers to questions from experts at any time (24/7) [3].

Conclusion. During the "Covid-19 pandemic" there were many shortages in the education sector, but teachers were encouraged to work remotely. In Uzbekistan, teachers have started to widely use distance education technologies. The electronic platform onlinedu.uz, created for remote training of public education pedagogues, was able to attract a large number of pedagogues by offering a wide range of opportunities. So far, 647053+ users are improving their skills.

Currently, scientific work is being carried out on the development of quality management mechanisms for professional development on the "Continuous Professional Education" platform. The influence of teachers is increasing day by day, and comfortable and wide opportunities are being created for them.

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